

**OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF FOREIGN BANKS IN INDIA: AN EMPIRICAL
ANALYSIS**

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Abstract

Indian banking system has transformed in recent years due to globalization in the world market, which has resulted in fierce competition. In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the operational performance of Foreign Banks in India. Analytical frame of the operational tools in terms of the Credit Deposit Ratio and Investment Deposit Ratio, and to different financial segments, purposes; and also the trends over the period under study have been presented. The study is based on secondary data collected from annual reports of five selected foreign banks in India for the study period i.e. 2000-01 to 2014-15. Ratios, t-test, correlation analysis have been used to analyze the present data. The study suggested that foreign banks in India should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, total investments, advances, deposits, debt and improving its operational efficiency.

Key words: *Operational Performance, Credit Deposits Ratio and Investment Deposits Ratio.*

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1. Introduction

India has a long history of both public and private banking. Modern banking in India began in the eighteenth century, with the founding of the English Agency House in Calcutta and Bombay. In the first half of the nineteenth century, three presidency banks were founded. After the 1860 introduction of limited liability, private banks began to appear, and foreign banks entered the market. The beginning of the twentieth century saw the introduction of joint stock banks. In 1935 the presidency banks were merged to form the Imperial Bank of India, subsequently renamed the State Bank of India. That same year, India's central bank, the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), began operation. Following independence, the RBI was given broad regulatory authority over commercial banks in India. In 1959 the State Bank of India acquired the state-owned banks of eight former princely states. Thus, by July 1969, approximately 31 percent of scheduled bank branches throughout India were government-controlled as part of the State Bank of India. India's post war development strategy was in many ways a socialist one, and the government felt that banks in private hands did not lend enough to those who needed it most.

The mandate given in the statute drives the corporation to develop entrepreneurship, bring in balanced regional development and drive the industrialization in the state in order to bring the economic development besides creating employment. The quantum of credit deposit ratio and Investment deposit ratios are the major indicators, which throw light on the performance of the foreign banks in fulfilling the responsibilities cast on them.

There are thirty-two (32) foreign banks which are presently operating in India through 308 branches with 1026 ATMs and 72.8% of offsite ATMs. Besides, there are 45 foreign banks operating through representative offices. Standard Chartered Bank, the oldest foreign bank that came to India 150 years ago is now operating with 95 branches. It is followed by HSBC, which entered India in 1867, with 50 branches. Citibank has 43 branches and ABN Amro Bank which is known by Royal Bank of Scotland N.V. at present has 31 branches. The other banks that have a double digit branch presence are Deutsche Bank (13) & DBS Bank (10). The enhanced number of branches (from 189 in 1998-1999 to 308 in 2009-2010) makes us curious about the functioning of FBs. Considering the present scenario, an evaluation of performance and efficiency level is needed about the functioning of FBs. This research study is an attempt to provide insights with respect to their functioning, profitability and productivity in post-liberalized regime.

2. Literature Review

1.Pigott (1986) in his study described the policies that have made increasing foreign bank activity possible in nine pacific basin countries, and he provided some aggregate statistics on the size and scope of foreign banking activities.

2.Nayak (2001) made an attempt to compare liquidity, productivity and profitability of foreign and domestic banks in India during 1985-86 to 1996-97. The results revealed the productivity in terms of labour, branches and profitability was higher in foreign banks than the domestic banks. Foreign banks are least involved in socio-economic policies of the government, on account of which they registered higher profits.

3.R.K Uppal and Rimpi Kaur (2006) elaborated about Globalization and banking Industry: Challenges and opportunities. Globalization is providing both an opportunity and challenges for Indian and foreign banks to expand their overseas operations. In India, leading foreign banks such as Standard Chartered Bank, Citi Bank, ABN AMRO Bank, etc have been carrying out their operations vigorously for over a decade with ambitious plans to expand them in rural areas as well. Similarly, many leading Indian banks, both public and private, have also been expanding their social banking and overseas activities by opening up overseas branches and expanding portfolio of their products and services for overseas operations. Being more IT and web-enabled and superior technology driven over the years, many overseas banks currently operating in India have long experience of overseas operations.

4.Sanyal and Shankar (2008) talk about the productivity differences that existed pre and post 1991 reforms and results shows that the productivity gap between Indian private banks, public and foreign banks has dramatically increased due to faster productivity growth by Indian private banks.

5.Pradeep Kumar Keshari (2013) The theory of globalization suggests that the multinational banks enjoy internationalisation advantage in overcoming imperfection in the international financial market. Affiliates of multinational banks foreign banks in India and elsewhere being part of a worldwide network have access to certain tangible and intangible resources which are not normally available, or only available in a limited amount to domestic banks. The tangible resources include, among other things, foreign funds and highly skilled manpower, while the intangible assets comprise of diversification advantage, management and marketing skills, know-how for introducing new products, better customer services, internationally established marketing network, reputation and goodwill, specialized information on financial market, etc.

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1.Pigott, Charles A., 1986 "Financial reform and the role of foreign banks in pacific basin nations", financial policy and reform in pacific-rim countries.

2.Nayak, D.N., 'Liquidity, Productivity and Profitability of Foreign Banks and Domestic Banks in India - A Comparative Analysis', Ibid., pp.305-20.

3.R.K Uppal & Rimpi Kaur : Globalization and banking Industry : Challenges and opportunities, Management & change , Volume, Number 2 (2006) IILM Institute of higher education

4.Sanyal, P. and Shankar, R. (2008), "Ownership, Competition and Bank Productivity: An Analysis of Indian Banking in the Post-Reform Period",

5.Pradeep Kumar Keshari(2013) Operational characteristics, strategies, and performance of foreign and domestic banks in India 22. May 2013 MDI Management Journal, Vol.7, No.2, (July 1994)

2. Research Objectives

Main objectives of the Paper is as follows

- ❖ To study and analyze the operational performance of Foreign Banks in India.
- ❖ To identify impact of profitability on Investment activities of Foreign Banks in India.

4. Research Hypotheses

For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis is to be tested:

H₁: Credit Deposit Ratio is tool for measuring operational performance of the selected five foreign banks in India.

H₂: Investment Deposit Ratio is tool for measuring operational performance of the selected five foreign banks in India.

5. Methodology

The design of the present study is descriptive and analytical in nature and covers the period of 15 years from 2000 to 2014. The data which is required for the analysis and that could fulfill our objectives has been collected mainly from two sources, viz 1) primary and 2) secondary data.

Primary data is collected from the officials and other employees through interviews and discussions with Experts, Chief Finance Officers, Finance Managers, Branch Managers and other Bank officers regarding different aspects of the five foreign banks.

The study is also based on the secondary data obtained from the audited balance sheets and profit & loss accounts, operational reports, budgets, manuals and also the annual reports of ABN AMRO, CITI Bank, Deutsche Bank, Chartered Standard Bank and HSBC. Besides, the facts, figures and findings advanced in similar earlier studies and the RBI Reports, International Financial Reports and government publications are also used to supplement the secondary data.

For assessing the behavior of data statistical techniques have been used such as descriptive, Mean, Standard Deviation, Range, Correlation, t-test, F test are used for this study. For these statistical measures are calculated by using SPSS software.

Credit Deposit Ratio

The particulars pertaining to Credit Deposit Ratio of all select foreign banks vis-a-vis all the foreign banks in the country are depicted in table 1. A quick glance at the table gives us an impression that there has been volatility with regard to movements of CD Ratios of national level as well as of select foreign banks. In other words, it is ranged from 72 per cent to 91 per cent for all foreign banks put together. A probe into performance of select foreign banks against the national average, reveals that both Citi bank and HSBC did have lower CD Ratios during 2006-07 indicating that these two banks were not able to make use of their deposit resources for the purpose of loans and advances. However, there has been a surge in CD Ratio movements of these two banks from 1999-2000 to 2013-14. A further probe into interbank performance of select banks discloses that which the ABN AMRO topped the list with regard to CD Ratios followed by Standard Chartered Bank, Deutsche Bank, Citi Bank and HSBC during 1999-2000, by the term of 2013-14, it was the Deutsche Bank ranked first followed by ABN AMRO, Standard Chartered Bank, Citi bank and HSBC. From that, it can be inferred that HSBC, though is placed in good position when compared to national figures, displayed descending figures of CD Ratio during the study period. This might be attributed to the strategy of ABN AMRO in reducing its reliance on deposit resources for loans and advances. As the performance of Citi bank and HSBC is not up to the mark, it is suggested that these two banks chalk out a strategy in improving their CD Ratios at least to be par with national averages.

It can be seen from the table 1 that the Credit Deposit Ratio is most favourable to the ABN AMRO its mean value and SD of this ratio was 104.16 times and 0.16.8 times. From this statistical analysis, it is evident that the total advances to total deposits ratio of the ABN is most favourable as compared to the other banks. It is indicated that ABM AMRO has maintained more advance to its deposits.

6. Analysis of the Study

Table -1: Credit Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014 (Rs. inCrores)

Year	ABN AMRO			CITI Bank			Deustche Bank			Standard Chartered Bank		
	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio
2000-01	4236	4610	91.89	9325	14052	66.36	2097	2322	90.31	5200	5088	102.20
2001-02	4487	4865	92.23	11385	15242	74.69	1888	2477	76.22	9033	7244	124.70
2002-03	5444	5022	108.40	12629	17743	71.18	1608	1945	82.67	13042	18003	72.44

200 3-04	6697	5856	114.3 6	15259	20465	74.56	2098	2533	82.83	16152	19949	80.97
200 4-05	9836	7026	139.9 9	18111	21484	84.30	2541	3558	71.42	19970	22522	88.67
200 5-06	15073	11864	127.0 5	24455	27912	87.61	2582	4380	58.95	24077	28460	84.60
200 6-07	18388	15998	114.9 4	32861	37875	86.76	4945	6978	70.87	30104	34174	88.09
200 7-08	20381	18912	107.7 7	38377	46125	83.20	8960	13755	65.14	33352	37004	90.13
200 8-09	16660	15960	104.3 9	39920	51677	77.25	8798	14147	62.19	37489	41802	89.68
200 9-10	13406	16601	80.75	36655	54452	67.32	12923	14693	87.95	41552	48192	86.22
201 0-11	10551	13947	75.65	40597	56668	71.64	14294	14646	97.60	49201	58419	84.22
201 1-12	12535	13040	96.13	47103	64698	72.80	12549	16843	74.51	55570	63965	86.88
201 2-13	12534	12749	98.31	52036	66559	78.18	22374	20794	107.6 0	61954	62149	99.69
201 3-14	11135	11626	95.78	56519	78313	72.17	29014	26114	111.1 1	68423	72112	94.88
Mea n	-	-	104.1 6	-	-	75.52	-	-	81.45	-	-	90.63
SD	-	-	16.89	-	-	7.26	-	-	15.54	-	-	11.83
Ran ge	-	-	64.34	-	-	22.76	-	-	52.16	-	-	52.26

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Table - 1: Credit Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014 (Rs. inCrores)

Year	HSBC			Select Foreign Banks			Total Foreign Banks		
	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio	Total Advances	Total Deposits	Credit Deposit Ratio
2000-01	6246	9951	62.77	27104	36023	75.24	43051	59240	72.67
2001-02	7836	12341	63.50	34629	42169	82.12	48632	64511	75.39
2002-03	8202	12801	64.07	40925	55514	73.72	52018	69110	75.27
2003-04	9628	16270	59.18	49834	65073	76.58	59822	79141	75.59
2004-05	12621	17013	74.18	63079	71603	88.10	75318	86389	87.18
2005-06	16812	24955	67.37	82999	97571	85.07	97562	113745	85.77
2006-07	23142	34825	66.45	109440	129850	84.28	126339	150750	83.81
2007-08	29944	42620	70.26	131014	158416	82.70	161959	191443	84.60
2008-09	27589	49970	55.21	130456	173556	75.17	165385	214076	77.26
2009-10	23475	55748	42.11	128011	189686	67.49	163260	232099	70.34
2010-11	27401	54107	50.64	142044	197787	71.82	195511	240667	81.24
2011-12	35512	61423	57.82	163269	219969	74.22	229849	276948	82.99
2012-13	35709	56866	62.79	184607	219117	84.25	263680	288144	91.51
2013-14	40218	71728	56.07	205309	259893	79.00	291154	352424	82.61
Mean	-	-	60.20	--	-	78.07	-	-	79.92
SD	-	-	8.38	-	-	6.06	-	-	6.22
Range	-	-	32.07	-	-	20.61	-	-	21.17

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Figure 1 shows the Credit Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014

Figure 1: Credit Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014

Investment Deposit Ratio:

Table 2 portrays the investment deposit ratio of foreign banks vis-a-vis all the foreign banks put together in the country during 2000-2014. As a measure to improve the financial performance, the banks have to make use of a purpose of investments and foreign banks are not at all exception to this .As evident from the table that the Investment Deposit Ratios of all the foreign banks together had been registered a contracting trend during 2000-2006, while a gradual upward movement was noticed since, 2006-07. The status of select banks against all against all foreign banks together reveals at the Citi Bank and HSBC recorded I-D ratios below the national average during 2000-2001, by the turn of 2013-14 apart from the Citi Bank, even ABN AMRO, Deustche Bank and Standard Chartered Bank, while there was a marked progression in respect of Citi Bank and HSBC, the diversified strategy of investment out of deposits resources among the select foreign banks.

It is found that the Investment Deposit Ratio is most favourable to the DUTCH BANK its mean was 76.43 times. For risk point of view least SD has observed to the SFB i.e. 21.27 times. This ratio is most favavourable to the DB as compared to the other four banks and it has taken higher risk. From this statistical analysis, it is evident that the total investments to total deposits have done more as compared the other banks by the DUTCH BANK. As output from this ratio for the past 15 years, it is most favourable. It is found that DUTCH BANK has done highest investment to their deposits.

Table - 2: Investment Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014 (Rs. inCrores)

Year	ABN AMRO			CITI Bank			Deutsche Bank			Standard Chartered Bank		
	Total Investm ents	Total Depos its	Investm ent Deposit Ratio	Total Investm ents	Total Depos its	Investm ent Deposit Ratio	Total Investm ents	Total Depos its	Investm ent Deposit Ratio	Total Investm ents	Total Depos its	Investm ent Deposit Ratio
2000-01	2857	4610	61.97	5603	14052	39.87	2430	2322	104.65	5401	5088	106.15
2001-02	2129	4865	43.76	6007	15242	39.41	1861	2477	75.13	7017	7244	96.87
2002-03	2985	5022	59.44	7036	17743	39.66	2459	1945	126.43	10223	18003	56.78
2003-04	2917	5856	49.81	6690	20465	32.69	2277	2533	89.89	10072	19949	50.49
2004-05	3331	7026	47.41	8120	21484	37.80	2254	3558	63.35	10160	22522	45.11
2005-06	4825	11864	40.67	10556	27912	37.82	3261	4380	74.45	10632	28460	37.36
2006-07	6407	15998	40.05	16021	37875	42.30	6204	6978	88.91	11902	34174	34.83
2007-08	11777	18912	62.27	18450	46125	40.00	10171	13755	73.94	12787	37004	34.56
2008-09	10811	15960	67.74	24519	51677	47.45	8705	14147	61.53	15552	41802	37.20
2009-10	7265	16601	43.76	28109	54452	51.62	9047	14693	61.57	18477	48192	38.34
2010-11	8902	13947	63.83	30399	56668	53.64	8598	14646	58.71	23088	58419	39.52
2011-12	7721	13040	59.21	43167	64698	66.72	8422	16843	50.00	27324	63965	42.72
2012-13	9124	12749	71.57	44077	66559	66.22	10601	20794	50.98	30747	62149	49.47
2013-14	5438	11626	46.77	51272	78313	65.47	19711	26114	75.48	28388	72112	39.37
MEAN	-	-	55.84	-	-	46.80	-	-	76.79	-	-	51.43
SD	-	-	12.16	-	-	11.35	-	-	21.27	-	-	21.96
RANGE	--	-	39.32	-	-	34.03	-	-	76.43	-	-	71.59

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Table-2 : Investment Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014

(Rs. inCrores)

Year	HSBC			Select Foreign Banks			Total Foreign Banks		
	Total Investment s	Total Deposits	Investment Deposit Ratio	Total Investment s	Total Deposits	Investment Deposit Ratio	Total Investment s	Total Deposits	Investment Deposit Ratio
2000-01	5792	9951	58.21	22083	36023	61.30	35584	59240	60.07
2001-02	6274	12341	50.84	23288	42169	55.23	35094	64511	54.40
2002-03	8870	12801	69.29	31573	55514	56.87	40716	69110	58.91
2003-04	10395	16270	63.89	32351	65073	49.71	40886	79141	51.66
2004-05	9169	17013	53.89	33034	71603	46.13	42858	86389	49.61
2005-06	12142	24955	48.66	41416	97571	42.45	52384	113745	46.05
2006-07	14131	34825	40.58	54665	129850	42.10	71471	150750	47.41
2007-08	19290	42620	45.26	72475	158416	45.75	99092	191443	51.76
2008-09	31154	49970	62.35	90741	173556	52.28	130354	214076	60.89
2009-10	41289	55748	74.06	104187	189686	54.93	159291	232099	68.63
2010-11	37279	54107	68.90	108266	197787	54.74	165499	240667	68.77
2011-12	40324	61423	65.65	126958	219969	57.72	200651	276948	72.45
2012-13	45179	56866	79.45	139728	219117	63.77	228063	288144	79.15
2013-14	56567	71728	78.86	161376	259893	62.09	260456	352424	73.90
MEAN	-	-	61.07	-	-	53.53	-	-	60.25
SD	-	-	11.93	-	-	6.95	-	-	10.34
RANGE	-	-	38.87	-	-	21.67	-	-	33.10

Source: IBA, Performance Highlights of Foreign Banks in India, Different Issues, Mumbai

Figure 2 shows the Investment Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014

Figure – 2: Investment Deposit Ratio of Select Banks and total Foreign Banks during the year 2000-01 to 2013-2014

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Correlation and t-test results for operational performance of selected five foreign banks

Variable	'r' value	Correlation result	't' critical value	't' value at correlation
CDR	0.72	High Positive and Significant	//2.447//	//2.29//
IDR	0.68	High Positive and Significant	//2.447//	//2.07//

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the Table: The correlation among all five foreign banks through its operational performance ratios i.e. Credit Deposit ratio and Investment Deposit Ratio. These two ratios of the five banks have high positive correlation and t values supported for correlation significant for all performance ratios to all selected banks. Overall outcome of the select foreign banks and total foreign banks are also consistent and significant the same supported by correlations result. Therefore we concluded that two performance ratios are useful to all selected foreign banks for measuring its operational performance assess.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

H₁: Credit Deposit Ratio is tool for measuring operational performance of the selected five foreign banks in India.

H₂: Investment Deposit Ratio is tool for measuring operational performance of the selected five foreign banks in India.

T- TEST RESULTS OF OPERATIONAL PERFORMANCE FIVE SELECTED BANKS, SELECT FOREIGN BANKS AND TOTAL FOREIGN BANKS

	Test Values					
	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
CDR	1.707	6	.139	25.71714	-11.1418	62.5761
IDR	1.837	6	.116	20.27143	-6.7328	47.2757

Source: Computed

It can be seen from the Table two performance ratios of the five selected foreign banks and select foreign banks and total foreign banks, t test values of all seven performance ratios more than the critical value at 5% level of significant. Here given hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, we concluded that all the foreign banks operational performance is similar.

Further, we concluded that the Credit Deposit ratio, Investment Deposit Ratios are very much relevant to measure the operational performance of the selected banks.

FINDINGS

- It is observed that total advances to total deposits have been maintained effectively by ABN AMRO and Standard Chartered Bank.
- It is found that Investment to Deposits and Interest Income performance good at ABN AMRO, Deutsche Bank and HSBC. These three banks have sufficient funds to meet its risk profile and generates more funds and utilized purposefully.
- CDR and IDR operational ratios of the five banks have high positive correlation and t values supported for correlation significant for all these performance ratios to all selected banks. Overall outcome of the select foreign banks and total foreign banks are also consistent and significant the same supported by correlations result.
- It is observed that CDR and IDR are useful to all selected foreign banks for measuring its operational performance assess. This result was statistically proved with correlation and t test.

To conclude, our findings from the operational performance of five selected foreign in India are moderate during the study period. It is suggested that foreign banks in India should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, debt, Investments and Deposits. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the foreign banks in India for better performance. To conclude, our findings from the productivity performance of five selected foreign in India are moderate during the study period. It is suggested that foreign banks in India should emphasize on generating more profits by efficient utilization of its capital, assets, debt, Investments and Deposits. Profitability of the investments and deployment of liquid assets (cash) should be cared for improved employee productivity efficiency. In addition to that diversification of lending, moderation of transaction costs and management of funds are very much influenced to the foreign banks in India for better productivity performance.

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